

STUDY OF SUMATERA SQUALL LINE USING WEATHER RADAR AND HIMAWARI-8 SATELLITE

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Abstract

Sumatras is a term for squall lines that usually appear between March and November every year on Sumatra Island and Malacca Strait. Sumatra Squall Line usually formed in the east coast of Sumatra, Malacca Strait, peninsular Malaysia, to Singapore on the night until early morning. This squall line grows every year and causes bad weather such as heavy rain and gusty winds that impact on flights around Malacca Strait. However, the study of Sumatras is still least concerned in Indonesia so this research is deemed necessary. This research is aimed to determine the vertical squall line structure and life cycle by using weather radar, satellite image and observation data from Pekanbaru Meteorological Station. The weather radar product used is CMAX, SRV, VCUT, VIL, and the Himawari 8 satellite image data used is the Infrared channel. In March 2018, Pekanbaru Meteorological Station weather radar detected a squall line phenomenon seen from the analysis of radar products. The land-based wind convergence from the eastern coast of Sumatra and the west coast of peninsular Malaysia led to wind convergence extending around the Malacca Strait. As a result, there are slight to moderate rain intensity and gusty winds around the area in a long time.

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1. Introduction

Indonesia as a maritim country has its own complexity on the atmosphere and also weather. One of the atmospheric phenomenon is squall lines. A squall line is defined as a line of active thunderstorms, either continuous or with breaks, including contiguous precipitation areas resulting from the existence of the thunderstorms [6]. The thunderstorm has a length about hundred kilometers and dozens in width, with live periode longer than a single cell thunderstorm [1]. Squall lines occur when there is a boundary layer convergence that cause a strong upward convection [5]. And it can produce heavy rains, damaging winds, hail, and sometimes even tornadoes.

Squall lines are linear or quasi-linear mesoscale convective systems (MCSs) that can appear in tropical area. Sumatras is a squall lines system on Malacca Straits which is surrounded by Indonesian Island, the Malay Peninsula and Singapore. This area consists of shallow seas, mountainous terrain, and also proximate to the equator, which can easily provide an abundance of moisture adding to the instability. Besides, the climate of these areas are dominated by two monsoon seasons, which has a prevailing winds and allow the pressure systems occur. Both of these are ideal conditions for the development of large convections systems, lead to the formation of Sumatras. Sumatras mostly appear between March and November every year. It usually forms on Sumatra Island or Malacca Straits moving to the east, and across Singapore, Peninsula Malaysia also Riau province on the night until early morning. Sumatras commonly damaging heavy winds and rains on surface in one or two hours [7]. If there are severe weather in Malacca Straits, it would be detrimental to the economical aspect in this stait, which is known as one of the busiest transportation line for both water and air. Besides, it can lead the hydrometeorological disasters in the area where the squall lines pass and occur. This research is done to knowing the meteorological conditions, squall line structure and life. This is consider to the high frequency of Sumatras phenomenon and cause extream weather in this area. By this research, hopefully can be used as a reference on Sumatras analysis and prediction in order to giving a weather warning.

2. Data and method

The data used in this study list as below :

- a. Enhanced himawari 8 satellite imagery from Indonesian Agency for Meteorology Climatology and Geophysics (BMKG).

- b. Wind data from WRF-ARW (Weather Research and Forecasting - Advanced Research) simulation.
- c. Hourly weather radar data from Syarif Kasim II Meteorological Station in Pekanbaru.
- d. Rain accumulation data from Global Satellite Mapping of Precipitation (GSMAP) data.

Each data used to identified both visual characteristic and impact of the squall line penetration in the region passed by the squall line and surrounding. This study conducted by using hourly data on 18th July 2018. The specific method performed in this study can be summarized as follows:

- a. Himawari 8 imagery also used to find out the visual pattern of sumatera squall line based on cloud top temperature wich is usually indicated by a low cloud top temperature by less than -40°C.
- b. Wind data used for analyse the wind pattern when the squall line occur, and where the air mass source is. Moreover, this data can be used to matches the wind pattern produced by weather radar data.
- c. Weather imagery analysis using reflectivity product CMAX to see the squall line specific pattern and VCUT to see the vertical patern of the storm. In most of squall line case, the cloud system shows an elongated pattern with specific pattern called bow echo or coma echo. Velocity product PPI used to identified the radial wind around the radar coverage. Furthermore, VIL used to estimated the liquid water content within the cloud in certain level.
- d. Rain accumulation obtained from observation data needed to ascertain the impact of sumatera squall line to the rainfall in the surrounding region.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Himawari-8 Satellite Analysis

Based on Himawary Satellite Imagery as shown in Figure 1, there was an indication of Sumatra Squall Line on July 18, 2018 at 21:00 UTC. This could be seen in the IR-Enhanced channel Himawary satellite imagery, there were convective clouds that cover the waters of Malacca Strait. The cloud top temperature ranged from -21°C to -58°C before the Sumatra Squall Line event, so it could be said that the convective clouds which occurred on that date indicated the existence of a meso-scale convective system. Cloud growth can be seen in the picture marked with a red circle. The formation of convective clouds began covered up part of the study area at 21:30 UTC, then continue to growed and elongated due to a strong convection process. In the mature phase, convective clouds expanded to form lines with stratiform clouds on the edges. The cloud top temperature also decreased to -62°C. At 23.30 UTC, the range of convective clouds began extincted and broken out which is characterized by convective cloud growth that does not formed a straight line anymore on July 19, 2018 at 00.00UTC. Based on Himawari-8 satellite image analysis, Sumatra Squall Line only lasts approximately 2 hours.

Figure 1. IR-Enhanced channel Himawary satellite imagery on July 18, 2018 at 21.00 UTC –

3.2. Wind Pattern Analysis

In Figure 2, there are 10 meter layer wind data. Before the Sumatra squall line happened on July 18 2018 at 21:00 UTC, the wind speed ranged from 6 m/s - 8 m/s from the southeast in the Malacca Strait waters. The tight wind vector indicates the wind speed in the formation of squall line area were faster than in other regions. Wind speed began to increased along with the formation of squall line up to 9 m/s. Increased wind speed results there were air mass association forming convective clouds in the Malacca Strait waters to form Sumatra Squall line. The existence of local influences seen in surface wind data shows that squall line which occurred in the Malacca Strait was Sumatra Squall line, while Squall line is generally formed as a result of global influences so this is distinguishes between Sumatran Squall Line and Squall Line in general. Wind direction from south to north due of the Australian monsoon that occurred at that time.

Figure 2. Wind speed and direction on July 18, 2018 at 21.00 UTC - July 19, 2018 at 00.00UTC

3.3. Radar Data Processing

3.3.1. Cmax

CMAX imagery can be used to analyze the life stages of the squall line by measuring the radar beam reflected by the storm. Squall line appears as a line of convective cell that is significantly longer than it is wide (Comet, 2013).. Based on CMAX imagery shown in Figure can be seen that the squall line early stage start before 21.00 UTC. This early stage indicated by several convective cells line up to form a line with reflectivity value ranged from 50 – 55 dBZ as marked by red circle. At the mature stage, there is intense convective cell (leading edge) followed by stratiform precipitation extending behind that occurred at 21.00 UTC. The squall line start to decay at 23.00 UTC, which indicated by the weakens of leading edge, but the stratiform precipitation still persist for several hour until 00.00 UTC. Overall, it can be seen that the development of sumateras squall line evolution occurs at 21.00 UTC until the next day at 00.00 UTC.

Figure 3. Weather radar product CMAX imagery on July 18, 2018 at 21.00 UTC - July 19, 2018 at 00.00UTC

3.3.2. VIL

VIL is a product that can show the value of moisture content in the atmosphere. If the VIL amount is big, it is possible for heavy rain to be formed. The moisture content detected by radar tends to develop in the south area of the radar with an intensity of 0.1 - 6.3 mm. The moisture content is seen increasingly moving towards the Northeast towards the Malacca Strait. This can be seen in radar observations on 20.06 UTC - 22.56 UTC, which then disappears afterwards. While in the west to northeast part of the radar there is a lower moisture content with a least intensity around 0.1 - 12.6 mm, the most dominant moisture content found in the Northwest area of radar observation. The red circle shown how the squall line in land area detected. Based on the VIL product, it shown that the system moved forward to the Malacca Strait with the intensity around 0.1 - 12.6 mm.

Figure 4. Weather radar product VIL imagery on July 18, 2018 at 21.00 UTC - July 19, 2018 at 00.00UTC

3.4. Rainfall Analysis

Figure 5 shows hourly rainfall intensity from GSMAP data. The rainfall intensity ranged from 1 - 20 mm/hour with the most intense rainfall observed at 21.00 UTC. Squall line indicated by intense rainfall in the front of the storm followed by stratiform precipitation behind as shown by the Figure 5. The precipitation tend to get a pattern like squall line shape with the highest intensity detected on the land of Malaysia. The system then moved forward to the west and touched the coastal area of Singapore. The rain intensity of the system became weak as its movement to Malacca Strait, and at the end of the day (23.58 UTC), it shown that rain intensity of the core system became 1.1 mm/hour.

Figure 5. GSMAP rainfall intensity on July 18, 2018 at 21.00 UTC - July 19, 2018 at 00.00UTC

4. Conclusions

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the Sumatra Squall Line phenomenon was the result of local influences. There were also influences from Australian monsoon that occurred at that time which blew from south to north so that it affected wind direction. The increase of wind speed in the Malacca Strait waters causes air mass associations that formed convective clouds. Convective clouds formed a straight line with stratiform clouds on the edges. So that there were increased of rainfall in parts of Malaysia, Singapore and Riau.

5. References

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